

"WAYS TO IMPROVE THE LIVING STANDARDS OF THE POPULATION"

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Annotation: *The textile industry is one of the drivers of changes in the living standards of the population. The action strategy sets tasks such as modernization and diversification of industry through a qualitatively new stage, increasing the processing of local raw materials, mastering the production of radically new types of products, increasing the competitiveness of domestic products. In the textile industry, foreign and domestic markets, localization of production and import substitution have been successfully implemented.*

Keywords: *Light industry, export, income, diversification, modernization, complex, technical and technological renewal .*

INTRODUCTION

The economic policy of Uzbekistan is based on the diversification and modernization of production, the creation of high-tech products with high added value, as well as increasing competitiveness and strengthening its position in world markets. Implementation of an active investment policy, technical modernization of industrial sectors and production infrastructure has allowed Uzbekistan to create new high-tech industries such as automotive, gas, chemical, electrical, mechanical engineering, building materials industries. , pharmaceuticals, furniture industry and others. Significant qualitative changes in the economy of our country in recent years. As a result of the adoption and consistent implementation of the priority program of industrial development for 2011-2015 and sectoral programs for modernization, technical and technological renewal of production in the industrial structure, it has the largest share in total capital investment. funds of republican enterprises .

Uzbekistan's industrial policy is export-oriented. Today, the production of non-commodity goods is competitive and increasingly export-oriented. Studies show that it is the export of finished products, especially those that require sophisticated science, that generates the most revenue. Technical and technological modernization of production in the structure of industry The largest share in the total volume of capital investments falls on the funds of enterprises of the republic. Uzbekistan's industrial policy is export-oriented. Today, the production of non-commodity goods is competitive and increasingly export-oriented. Studies show that it is the export of finished products, especially those that require sophisticated science, that generates the most revenue. Technical and technological modernization of production in the structure of industry The largest share in the total volume of capital investments falls on the funds of enterprises of the republic. Uzbekistan's industrial policy is export-oriented. Today, the production of non-commodity goods is competitive and increasingly export-oriented. Studies show that it is the export of finished products, especially those that require sophisticated science, that generates the most revenue.

Modernization, technical and technological renewal of production as the most important condition for rising to a qualitatively new level of development. Uzbekistan has adopted a program of measures to restructure, modernize and diversify production in 2015-2019, which provides for the implementation of 846 investment projects worth \$ 40.81 billion. . 846 investment projects are being implemented in Uzbekistan within the program approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 4, 2015 "On modernization and diversification of production in 2015-2019". The total cost of technological modernization of production facilities is 40.809 billion soums.

The implementation of the program is expected to provide an average annual GDP growth in 2015-2019. at least 8%, industrial production - 9%. As a result, the share of industry in Uzbekistan's GDP in 2022 will increase from the current 24% to 27%.

In 2015, Uzbekistan launched about 100 new product groups (about 1,000 types of assortment) and by 2020 will increase the annual production and export

potential of the industry by 18 trillion soums or \$ 2 billion, respectively. In particular, 124 investment projects on modernization, technical and technological renewal of production in Uzbekistan, as well as 48 new promising investments with the participation of foreign investors in the fields of geology, fuel and energy, chemical, petrochemical and metallurgical industries project is planned.

The main directions of development of diversification of industrial enterprises. The main results of the production of light industry goods. Among the known methods of reforming the activities of light industry enterprises, the most effective is to change their composition and product types, ie diversification. The experience of highly developed foreign countries has shown that diversification provides stability to the activities of organizations, weakens their dependence on individual market conditions and provides a strong connection to different consumer groups. Diversification of production can and should be considered as one of the strategic alternatives to long-term planning for the development of light industry enterprises.

METHOD AND RECOMMENDATION:

The textile industry is one of the most developed in Uzbekistan. Industrial enterprises produce yarn, yarn, raw materials and finished fabrics. Knitwear and sewing - the production of clothing and household goods is developed. The importance of the development of this sector of the economy for Uzbekistan is primarily due to the availability of its own raw material base (cotton, silk, wool), as well as the relatively high labor intensity of the textile industry. an industry that plays an important role in addressing employment issues and improving the living standards of the population.

World experience shows that the development of the textile industry can be explosive when favorable conditions are available. At the same time, there is a significant increase in value added due to deep processing of raw materials, which will increase the income of the population, enterprises and the state, as well as ensure high growth rates of exports and reduce imports (ready-made clothes).). During the years of independence, the light industry of Uzbekistan has taken a strong place in

the industrial complex of our country. Thanks to the created favorable conditions, privileges and preferences, a strong regulatory framework, the enterprises of the industry have achieved great success and are entering a qualitatively new stage of development. As a result, over the years of independence, the role of light industry in the economy of Uzbekistan has increased significantly, its share in GDP was 3.8 %, industrial production - 26.2%, industrial production - 26.2%. non-food consumer goods account for more than 44% [1]. The volume of cotton fiber processing in the country has increased from 7% in 1991 to 35% of the total volume of cotton fiber produced in the country in 2014. In the last 3 years alone, 92 industrial enterprises with a total value of 575.3 million US dollars and an export potential of 215.8 million US dollars have been launched, more than 11.6 thousand jobs have been created, including:

JV Indorama Kokand Textile LLC with a production capacity of 29,000 tons of yarn per year was established for the Kokand Textile Combine (project cost \$ 110 million) ;

- Uztex Group in cooperation with Swiss Capital (Switzerland) has organized the production of 12,000 tons of cotton yarn per year in Khorezm region, the total cost of the project is more than 50 million US dollars.

- The former Uzbektexilemash LLC Rieter AG, a Swiss company Mashinenfabrik, has created Riter Uzbekistan, a manufacturer of ribbon, combing and spinning machines, as a result of which the textile industry in the country has been restored to a modern level.

Production indicators of Uzbekyengilsanoat JSC: product export, localization program and implementation of investment program. In 2015, Uzbekyengilsanoat JSC and enterprises will produce consumer goods worth 1327.1 billion soums, which is 125% more than in the same period last year . , 9 percent, and industrial production was 125.9 percent. Products worth 3159.7 billion soums were produced, the growth rate was 122.0%. Physically, the production of the main types of products was provided, including: cotton yarn - 307.1 thousand tons (growth rate of 119.1%); cotton fabrics - 182.9 million square meters (118.1%); knitted fabric - 53.0 thousand

tons (111.1%); knitwear - 218.3 million pieces (144.3%); socks - 38.9 million pairs (133.2%); garments - 29.1 billion soums (126.1%); non-woven products - 37.0 million square meters (113.8%); raw silk yarn - 1077.7 tons (118.0%); water - 27.5 thousand tons (108.3%) [1]. [2]. In 2015, industrial enterprises produced 75 types of light industry products. 34.9 million square meters of cotton fabrics were mastered and produced. meters (filter fabrics, Avisen, tent fabrics, canvas fabrics, waffle fabrics, technical fabrics, “jeans” type cotton fabrics, etc.), 164 pieces of ready-made clothes and knitted products 20.5 million pieces. In total , more than 205.0 billion soums of new products were produced. In 2015, the volume of exports amounted to 865.1 million dollars. The share of finished products in total exports (\$ 315.9 million) is 36.5%. The decline in market prices of manufactured products by 15-20% compared to the same period last year had a significant impact on the export function [5]. New types of products were exported: compact yarn, tent fabrics, knitted garments, household textiles, melange yarn, poplin, technical fabrics, baby diapers, labels , etc. (about 50 countries around the world). Taking into account the stable and growing demand for cotton products in the world commodity market , the work on the development of export geography, the search for alternative markets (Europe, America and Southeast Asia) is carried out on a regular basis. This year, new markets from countries such as Canada, Colombia, and Saudi Arabia have been mastered. More than 13 textile enterprises supply products to the People's Republic of China. Currently, there are more than 40 dealer centers of large enterprises - exporters in the European Union, CIS and Asia.

CONCLUSION:

The conceptual approach to enterprise diversification management involves considering it as an important element of the set of economic and managerial relations that emerge and provide interactions between regional entities. Therefore, theory and methodology are required for the operation of the diversification process management system to achieve a complex effect.

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